

Phase Transfer Catalysis. Part-II¹ : Studies of a Few Michael Reactions of Synthetic Utility under Phase Transfer Catalysis

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A few Michael condensations with ethyl cyanoacetate, diethyl malonate, benzyl cyanide, *o*-methylbenzyl cyanide and benzyl methyl ketone as donors and 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (mesityl oxide), ethyl acrylate, methyl crotonate and methyl α,α -dimethylacrylate as acceptors under phase transfer catalysis (in presence of benzyltriethylammonium chloride and K_2CO_3) have been carried out. The method is superior to conventional base-catalysed Michael reaction with regards to yields which are often excellent. Substrates like ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate and 3,4-dihydro-1-(2H)-naphthalenone (1-tetralone) which are resistant to Michael addition also undergo condensation with mesityl oxide, although in low yield, under phase transfer catalysis. Some of the products are useful synthetic intermediates.

FROM 1965 onwards, due largely to the pioneering work of Makosza, Starks and Brandström, phase transfer catalysis (PTC) has emerged as a very powerful technique with almost unlimited applicability in synthetic and industrial chemistry. The method dispenses with expensive anhydrous solvents, allows the reactions to go at an enhanced rate, simplifies the reaction conditions and work-up procedure, often avoids undesired side reactions and is thus preferable to conventional methods when applicable. The importance of PTC may be realised from the large number of papers (well over thousand) and numerous reviews²⁻⁵ published on this topic during the last decade. Briefly stated, the principle involves the use of two immiscible phases—an aqueous phase containing a reservoir of a salt, M^+Nu^- , expected to function as base or nucleophile and an organic phase containing the substrate, RX , expected to react with the salt⁶. A phase transfer catalyst, Q^+X^- , generally a quaternary ammonium or phosphonium salt with a lipophilic cation when added into the mixture under vigorous stirring, exchanges anions giving an ion-pair, Q^+Nu^- , which distributes itself in both the phases and allows the reaction to go in the organic phase with the formation of RNu and Q^+X^- , the latter returning to the aqueous phase and thus completing the cycle. There are variations in which the aqueous phase is replaced by a solid phase or by crown ethers some times even in a three phase system. Numerous reactions of general applicability such as nucleophilic substitution, formation of dihalocarbenes, ethers and esters, alkylation, acylation, oxidation, reduction, halogenation, addition, elimination and others are successfully carried out under PTC condition. Asymmetric syntheses have also been achieved using chiral phase transfer

catalysts⁷. We report here a few Michael condensations of selected CH acids with α,β -unsaturated ketones and esters under PTC leading to products which will be subsequently used in some projected syntheses.

The following acceptors and donors are selected for the present Michael reactions.

Acceptors	Donors
$CH_2=CO-CH=CMe_2$ (A)	$NC-CH_2-CO_2Et$ (M)
$CH_2=CH-CO_2Et$ (B)	$EtO_2C-CH_2-CO_2Et$ (N)
$CH_2=CH-CH-CO_2Me$ (C)	$C_6H_5CH_2CN$ (O)
$(CH_3)_2C=CH-CO_2Me$ (D)	<i>o</i> -Me $C_6H_4-CH_2CN$ (P)
	$C_6H_5CH_2COCH_3$ (Q)

Most of them have been previously used in conventional Michael reactions⁸ and some of the donors like ethyl cyanoacetate, diethyl malonate, benzyl cyanide and benzyl methyl ketone been exhaustively studied for alkylation using phase transfer catalysis⁹. The normal procedure for alkylation is to use a catalytic⁹ or an equivalent¹⁰ amount of a quaternary ammonium or phosphonium salt in an organic phase in contact with aqueous 50% sodium hydroxide¹¹. The method when applied to Michael reactions suffers from the disadvantage that the ester group is often hydrolysed and in some cases, the acceptor molecules partially resinify. Recently, Yanovskaya *et al*¹² have reported a modified procedure in which the aqueous alkaline phase is replaced by anhydrous sodium or potassium carbonate, specially useful for α,β -unsaturated aldehydes. After a few trials, we found that a combination of anhydrous K_2CO_3 and benzyltriethylammonium chloride (BTEAC) in catalytic amount in benzene worked very well for all the Michael additions reported here. The procedure may very well be a general one for Michael reactions involving moderately strong

carbon acids. Substrates like ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (I) and 3,4-dihydro-1-(2H)-naphthalenone which are ordinarily resistant to Michael addition, also undergo condensation with mesityl oxide (A), although in low yield, under phase transfer catalysis.

Experimental

All melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on Perkin-Elmer Infra-cord spectrophotometer, model 237B in CHCl_3 . ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian EM 390 90 MHz machine using SiMe_4 as internal standard and CDCl_3 as solvent. GLC was done on a Varian gas chromatograph, model 3700 using FFAP (15%) column. Petroleum refers to a fraction, b.p. 40-60°. All organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

General procedure for phase transfer catalysis: In a typical experiment, a mixture of ethyl cyanoacetate (22.6 g; 0.2 mole), 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (19.6 g; 0.2 mole), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (28.0 g; 0.2 mole), benzyltriethylammonium chloride (1.0 g) and dry benzene was stirred vigorously at 65-70° for 4 hr. A further quantity of BTEAC (0.5 g) was added and stirring continued for another 4 hr. The yellow mixture was decomposed with water (200 ml), the benzene layer separated and the aqueous layer once extracted with ether (100 ml). The combined organic extracts were washed with water (100 ml), dried and distilled. For condensation of benzyl cyanide and ethyl acrylate, an excess (1.5-2.0 mole) of benzyl cyanide was used in order to get the monoalkylated product (80%). In condensations with methyl α,α -dimethylacrylate, two equivalents of the ester was used. Purity of products was checked by glc. When chloroform was used as solvent (temp. 45-50°), the yield of the above reaction dropped down to 50%.

Dialkylated products: The dialkylated product from benzyl cyanide and ethyl acrylate boiled at 210-215°/10 mm (yields, 15-50%); ν_{max} : 2250 and 1730 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 68.50; H, 7.35. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_4$ requires C, 68.14; H, 7.25%). Equimolecular quantities of *o*-methylbenzyl cyanide and ethyl acrylate afforded monoalkylated (85%) and dialkylated products (15%), b.p. 210-215°/10 mm; ν_{max} : 2250 and 1735 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 65.48; H, 7.65. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_4$ requires C, 68.88; H, 7.56%). No appreciable dialkylated products are detected in other reactions.

4-Cyano-5,5-dimethyl-4-phenethylcyclohexa-1,3-dione (VII): Ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (I) (4.34 g; 0.02 mole) was added to ethanolic sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.70 g; 0.031 mole) and dry ethanol (15 ml). 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one (3.92 g; 0.04 mole) was added and the mixture refluxed for 7 hr. The excess of alcohol was removed and the residue diluted with water. Neutral matter was extracted with ether and the

alkaline solution acidified. The resulting oily mass was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (3 × 30 ml) and the extract dried. The solvent was evaporated to afford a gum (4.5 g). This was heated in a saltbath at 180° for 2 hr (to decompose any substituted cyanoacid) and the residue was taken up in aqueous NaHCO_3 . After removal of neutral matter and acidification, a gummy residue (2.5 g) was obtained which on trituration with ether (5 ml) afforded 4-cyano-5,5-dimethyl-4-phenethylcyclohexa-1,3-dione (VII) (1.10 g, 20%), m.p. 139° (from aqueous methanol); ν_{max} (KBr): 2250, 1615, 1575, and 1525 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 75.70; H, 7.17. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2$ requires C, 75.83; H, 7.1%).

Methyl 3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (X): The substituted ethyl cyanoester (VII) was hydrolysed with conc. HCl and the acid esterified with methanolic HCl to afford methyl 3,3-dimethyl-5-oxohexanoate (X), b.p. 110°/10 mm; ν_{max} : 1710 and 1735 cm^{-1} ; δ (ppm): 3.70 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.60 (2H, s, 4- CH_2), 2.48 (2H, s, 2- CH_2) and 1.12 (6H, s, CMe_2).

2-(*o*-Methylphenyl)-glutaric acid: The cyanoester (XII) (20.0 g) was hydrolysed with a refluxing mixture of conc. HCl (50.0 ml) and acetic acid (20.0 ml). The resultant acid (18.0 g) crystallised from ether-petroleum in nodules, m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 64.55; H, 6.50. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.86; H, 6.31%). This was refluxed with acetic anhydride (4 vol) on a sand-bath for 4 hr to afford the anhydride which crystallised from ether-petroleum in colourless prisms, m.p. 85°; ν_{max} : 1810 and 1760 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 70.35; H, 6.00. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88%).

8-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthoic acid (XIX): The above anhydride (7.0 g) was treated with anhydrous AlCl_3 (9.0 g) in nitrobenzene (90 ml) at 0°. After 2 days at room temp. the red mixture was decomposed with ice and conc. HCl and nitrobenzene, distilled off with steam. The solid residue was taken up in CH_2Cl_2 and the residue after evaporation esterified with 5% ethanolic hydrogen chloride. The ester (as XVIII), (6.5 g), b.p. 145-150°; ν_{max} : 1732 and 1682 cm^{-1} , was hydrolysed with alkali to afford 8-methyl-4-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-naphthoic acid (XVIII), m.p. 149° (from aqueous methanol). (Found: C, 70.40; H, 5.95. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88%). This was smoothly hydrogenated by using Pd/C in acetic acid-ethyl acetate admixed with a little HClO_4 . The acid (XIX) was obtained as a crystalline solid, m.p. 146° (lit.²³ m.p. 146-148°).

2-Oxo-10-nor-podocarpa-1(10),8,11,13-tetraene (XXII): (a) *Under phase transfer catalysis:* A solution of Makosza's reagent, prepared from BTEAC (2.2 g) and aqueous 50% sodium hydroxide (20 ml) was added within a period of 1 hr to a stirring mixture of 1-tetralone (1.4 g) and mesityl oxide (2.5 g). After stirring for 5 hr methanolic 1% sodium hydroxide (50 ml) was introduced and the

stirring continued for 2 hr more. Methanol was removed, the organic matter extracted with CH_2Cl_2 , the extract dried and solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled *in vacuo* to afford a middle fraction, b.p. 180-190°/0.5 mm. It was absorbed on activated alumina (15 g) and eluted with petroleum-ether (95 : 5). After an initial fraction of some oily materials, the ketone (XXII) was eluted as a solid (0.45 g, 20%) which crystallised from benzene-petroleum in white prisms, m.p. 126°; ν_{max} : 1660 and 1595 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH): 230 and 295 nm (log 4.18 and 4.51, respectively). (Found: C, 85.15; H, 8.15. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.90; H, 7.90%). ^1H NMR spectrum is detailed in Table 2. It formed a red dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 13.95. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires N, 13.80%).

(b) *With potassium *t*-butoxide*²⁵: To a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide, prepared from potassium (1.20 g) and dry *t*-butanol (30 ml), 1-tetralone (4.0 g) was added followed by mesityl oxide (3.5 g). The red solution was gently refluxed under nitrogen for 4 hr. The product was worked up in the usual way and furnished an oil, b.p. 180-190°/0.5 mm. This was adsorbed on a column of alumina (50 g) and eluted with petroleum-ether (95 : 5). The tricyclic ketone (XXII) was obtained as a crystalline solid (0.6 g, 10%), m.p. 123°. It showed identical spectral behaviour as the one prepared under (a).

Results and Discussion

Our initial objective of using 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (A) in Michael reaction was to develop a simple route to 2-oxopodocarpa-8,11,13-triene (VI) following the reaction sequence shown in Scheme 1. Michael condensation of ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (I) (or malonate) with (A) is expected to give the ketocynoester (II) which on hydrolysis, decarboxylation, esterification and internal Claisen condensation should form the diketone (III). This would give the enol ether (IV) regioselectively²⁵ which on reaction with MeMgI followed by acidification should lead to the cyclohexenone (V), later to be cyclised to a stereoisomeric mixture of 2-oxopodocarpatriene (VI) following a recent method of Davis *et al*¹⁴. However, all attempts to condense diethyl phenethylmalonate with 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (A) proved abortive although similar reactions are well-precedented²⁵. Apparently, mesityl oxide undergoes self condensation prior to addition, the liberated water hydrolyses one of the carboethoxy group and ethyl 4-phenyl-2-carboethoxybutyric acid was isolated as the only acidic product. Use of ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate (I) and one equivalent of NaOEt was more effective affording the cyanocyclohexanedione (VII) in approximately 20% yield. The angular cyano group, however, could not be hydrolysed without disrupting the cyclohexanedione system.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—YIELDS, PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF THE MICHAEL ADDUCTS

Entry No.	Reactants	Product	Temp. /Time (°C/hr)	Yield (%)	b.p. (°C/mm)	n _D ²⁰	IR absorption frequency (cm ⁻¹)			Mol. formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
							C≡N	C-O	CO ₂ Et		C	H
1.	A+M	(VIII)	65-70/8	93	140/10	1.4470	2270	1717	1733	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃	62.10 (62.56)	8.35 (8.05)
2.	A+N	(IX)	65-70/8	55	140/10	1.4384	-	1720	1733	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	60.15 (60.47)	8.60 (8.53)
3.	B+O	(XI)	55-60/8	50-80 ^a	175/10	1.5026	2263	-	1730	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃	71.55 (71.89)	7.35 (6.91)
4.	B+P	(XII)	55-60/8	85 ^b	180/10	1.5035	2250	-	1730	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃	72.50 (72.73)	7.60 (7.36)
5.	B+Q	(XV)	65-68/10	95	170/10	1.4978	-	1708	1725	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	72.05 (71.79)	8.10 (7.69)
6.	C+O	(XIII)	65-70/10	70	165/8	1.5050	2250	-	1735 ^c 1727	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO ₃	71.65 (71.89)	7.25 (6.91)
7.	C+Q	(XVI)	65-70/10	70	160/8	1.5034	-	1710	1725	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	71.55 (71.79)	8.00 (7.69)
8.	D+O	(XIV)	65-70/10	10-15	160/8	1.5130	2250	-	1730	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃	72.25 (72.73)	7.65 (7.36)
9.	D+Q	(XVII)	65-70/10	<10	160/6	1.5208	-	1710	1725	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ O ₃	72.15 (72.58)	8.25 (8.06)
10.	A+(I)	(II)	70-75/20	30	185/0.1	1.5262	2270	1702	1733	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₃	71.85 (72.38)	8.25 (7.94)

^aThe remainder was dialkylated product ; a ratio of 2 : 1 moles of donor and acceptor gave 80% monoalkylated product.

^bThe remainder was dialkylated product (see Experimental). ^cTwo stereoisomers are formed.

We next carried out the Michael addition of diethyl malonate and ethyl cyanoacetate with mesityl oxide (A) under PTC in a systematic manner and observed that using anhydrous K₂CO₃ as a solid phase and BTEAC as catalyst, the yields of addition products (VIII) and (IX) were 93 and 55%, respectively (see Table 1) and the method was superior to conventional base-catalysed Michael reaction. Neither of the product, however, could be further alkylated with phenethyl bromide. Subsequently, ethyl phenethylcyanoacetate was allowed to react with mesityl oxide under the above condition for a prolonged period (20 hr) and 5 cyano-5-carboethoxy-4,4-dimethyl-7-phenylheptan-2-one (II) obtained in 30% yield. Diethyl phenethylmalonate, however, did not react. In view of the easy availability of the starting materials, the method may be synthetically useful inspite of the low yield and further work will follow from our laboratory.

We like to record here an observation on the ¹H nmr spectra of the substituted cyanoesters (II) and (VIII). The protons of the ketomethylene group appeared as AB-quartets, those of VIII resonating at δ 2.55 with Δ_{ν_{AB}} and J_{AB} values of 12.6 and 18 Hz, respectively. While this geminal nonequivalence is not surprising in compounds containing chiral centre three bonds apart¹⁶, high Δ_{ν_{AB}} is possibly due to strongly preferred conformation of the methylene protons with respect to CN and CO₂Et, influenced in some obscure way by the intervening CMe₂ linkage. That the geminal dimethyls at β-position do exert considerable steric hindrance¹⁷ and influence the nature of coiling of these compounds is further evidenced from our

failure to convert the keto-ester (X) into cyclic ketal by conventional procedure¹⁸.

A few more Michael reactions using the acceptors-donors listed earlier were carried out under the above phase transfer catalysis conditions. The results, shown in Table 1, clearly demonstrate the superiority of the procedure, the first seven combinations (entries 1-7) giving 55-95% yields of the adducts. The following observations are made in this connection. i) Benzene proved to be a better solvent than chloroform when the reactions are catalysed by BTEAC in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ giving cleaner products with higher yields. ii) In all the cases using molar ratio of the reactants, monoalkylated products are obtained predominantly if not exclusively. Only for condensation of benzyl cyanide and ethyl acrylate (entry 3) (both sterically unhindered), substantial amount of dialkylated product was formed which could be avoided by using two equivalents of the donor molecule. iii) As the bulk of the acceptor molecule increases, for example, methyl β,β-dimethylacrylate (entries 8 and 9), the yields of the adducts dropped down considerably and are lower than those available by conventional procedure¹⁹. We suggest that in such cases the bulky ion-pair, Q⁺Nu⁻, finds it difficult to approach the crowded site of the acceptor molecule and the conventional metallic salt, Na⁺Nu⁻, is more effective. This can be a general disadvantage of reactions carried out by phase transfer catalysts.

The products were characterised by spectral data (ir and nmr). ¹H NMR spectra of a few important compounds are summarised in Table 2. The

(XVIII)

(XIX)

(XX)

 TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA^a OF SOME MICHAEL ADDUCTS

Compound	Chemical shifts (δ ppm) (position, proton count, multiplicity and assignment)
(II)	7.14 (5H, br. s, ArH), 4.16 (2H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, OCH_2Me), 2.87-2.00 (6H, m, $3 \times CH_2$) ^b , 2.05 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.31-1.13 (9H, m, $3 \times CH_3$).
(VIII)	4.12 (2H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, OCH_2Me), 4.02 (1H, s, α -H), 2.42 (2H, AB-q, $J = 18$ Hz, $COCH_3$), 1.90 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.20, 1.10, 1.00 and 0.90 (9H, m, $3 \times CH_3$).
(IX)	4.20 (4H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, $2 \times OCH_2Me$), 4.12 (1H, s, α -H) 2.50 (2H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.95 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.20-0.90 (12H, m, $4 \times CH_3$).
(XI)	7.40 (5H, s, ArH), 4.17 (2H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, OCH_2Me), 4.00 (1H, t, 4-H) ^c , 2.45 (2H, t, $J = 7$ Hz, 2- H_2), 2.22 (2H, m, 3- H_2), 1.23 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3).
(XII)	7.35 (4H, m, ArH), 4.16 (3H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, $OCH_2Me + 4-H$), 2.52 (2H, t, $J = 7$ Hz, 2- H_2), 2.38 (3H, s, Ar CH_3), 2.20 (2H, m, 3- H_2), 1.27 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3).
(XIII)	7.42 (5H, s, ArH), 4.10 and 3.92 ^d (1H, 2 \times d, $J = 6$ Hz, 4-H), 3.70 and 3.63 ^d (3H, 2 \times s, CO_2Me), 2.43 (2H, t, 2- H_2), 2.10 (1H, m, 3-H), 1.07 (3H, m, 3-Me).
(XV)	7.40 (5H, m, ArH), 4.20 (2H, q, $J = 7$ Hz, OCH_2Me), 3.73 (1H, t, 4-H), 2.20 (4H, m, $2 \times CH_2$), 2.08 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.25 (3H, t, $J = 7$ Hz, OCH_2CH_3).
(XVI)	7.34 (5H, s, ArH), 3.67 and 3.57 ^d (3H, 2 \times d, CO_2Me), 2.10 (2H, m, 2- CH_2), 2.80 (1H, m, 4-H), 2.10 (2H, m, 2- H_2), 2.07 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 1.03 and 0.71 ^d (3H, 2 \times d, $J = 6$ Hz, 3- CH_2).
(XXII)	7.80 (1H, m, 11-H), 7.27 (3H, m, ArH), 6.70 (1H, d, $J = 2$ Hz, 1-H), 2.90 (3H, m, 5- $H_2 + 7-H_2$), 2.32 (2H, s, 3- H_2), 1.90 (2H, m, 6- H_2), 1.20 and 0.95 (6H, 2 \times s, 4-Me ₂).

^aSpectra were recorded on a Varian EM 390 90 MHz machine in $CDCl_3$.

^bAB-q of $COCH_3$ was centred at $\delta 2.60$ but overlapped with other signals.

^cNumbering of C-atoms refers to the side chain.

^dThe duplicity was due to the presence of two diastereomers.

^eSplitting was due to allylic 5-H.

compound (XIII) shows two ester bands in ir (1727 and 1735 cm^{-1} , entry 6) of equal intensity, being a mixture of two diastereomers. ^1H NMR spectra are also consistent with these observations (Table 2). Many of the Michael adducts may be used for further synthetic work. Thus, the cyanoester (XII) obtained in high yield (entry 4) was hydrolysed to 2-arylglutaric acid and the derived anhydride cyclised under Friedel-Crafts condition quantitatively to the keto-acid (XVIII). This was hydrogenated²⁰ to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-8-methyl-1-naphthoic acid (XIX)²¹, recently prepared by a more circuitous and difficult route²². We intend to convert it into 8-methyl-1-acetonaphthone (XX)²³ and a few derivatives thereof to be subsequently studied by dynamic nuclear magnetic resonance for measurement of *peri*-interaction in naphthalene system²⁴.

In 1957, the tricyclic ketone (XXII) was prepared in our laboratory²⁴ by condensation of 1-tetralone with mesityl oxide in presence of KOBU^t . The structure was confirmed by ^1H nmr and also by its conversion into 1-methylphenanthrene²⁵ but the yield (10%) was low. The reaction when carried out under PTC using BTEAC and K_2CO_3 , did not go, the starting materials being recovered unchanged. In view of weak acidity of 1-tetralone and unfavourable steric factor of the reaction, the failure was not unexpected. The procedure which appeared to work best was to stir a mixture of the two reactants with Makosza's reagent ($\text{PhCH}_2\text{N}^+\text{Et}_3\text{OH}^-$ in water) and then to convert the two-phase system to a single phase by adding a mutual solvent (methanol). The basic idea was not to isolate the diketone existing as a salt (XXI) (Scheme 2) but to allow it to pass into the aqueous phase where it was converted into the tricyclic ketone (XXII) by an internal aldol condensation. The yield (ca 20%) was, however, not greatly improved. It is possible that tetrabutylammonium cyanide in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (an one-phase reaction instead of two-phase)²⁶ may be more effective for this Michael reaction.

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